

**ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION OF TENTH STANDARD
GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SCHOOL STUDENTS IN
SOCIAL SCIENCE CURRICULUM: A
COMPARATIVE STUDY**

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Abstract:

The aim of the study is to compare the achievement motivation of X Standard government and private school students in Social Science curriculum. A sample of 425 government school and 425 private school X Standard students from Thanjavur, Kumbakonam and Pattukkottai Educational Districts were chosen using Simple Random Sampling method. Achievement Motivation Scale, developed and validated by the investigator and the guide (2015) with 33 items having five options was used as the tool. 't' test was used to compare the achievement motivation of X Standard government and private school students. The study revealed the following: The level of achievement motivation of X Standard government and private school students were found to be moderate. No significance of difference in achievement motivation was found between government and Private School Students in Social Science Curriculum with regard to (i) Boys, (ii) Girls, (iii) Tamil medium students, (iv) English medium students, and (v) Boys' school, (vi) Girls' school, and (vii) co-education school.

Key Words: Achievement Motivation, Tenth Standard Students, Government School & Private School

Introduction:

"Education, as a planned endeavour, at a personal level on a small scale or institutional level on a large scale, aims at making children capable of becoming active, responsible, productive, and caring members of society" (NCERT, 2009). Therefore "School education must be provided to all. ... There should be no distinction made in terms of the type of schooling provided within the government system for children from different social, economic and cultural backgrounds" (National Knowledge Commission, 2009). With a vision to impart education to all the citizens of the country in this massive task, both the government and private organizations are involved and both are running schools. Speculations over the differences continue to remain between these two types of schools, on many grounds including academic achievement, though the ultimate goal remains single. Academic achievement is one of the basic expectations and expected outcome. Students have to achieve and yet 'student achievement' or 'academic achievement of students' has a vital and decisive role in deciding the not only the academic success but also life success. Multiple factor like achievement movement, the facilities available in the school, the nature of school, the individual differences, learning environment at home, role and support of the parents and socio-economic factors affect the academic achievement. "Achievementmotivation is the person's tendency to achieve special goals" (Hassanzadeh, & Mahdinejad, n.d). This study specifically attempts to compare the achievement motivation of government and private school students in social science.

Significance of the Study:

The Secondary School Leaving Certificate (S.S.L.C.) Mark sheet includes Social Science as one of the subjects and any student of X standard ought to score the minimum pass marks, or else the student would be declared fail. No doubt, academic achievement in Social Science too becomes valuable and significant contributor in deciding the further continuation of studies. The investigator, being a teacher trainee who had selected History, a major component of Social Science subject, in his graduation and post-graduation studies, has a special interest and affinity, to pursue research in his subject. In this research, he has attempted to make a comparative study of achievement motivation of tenth standard government and private school students in Social Science curriculum.

Achievement Motivation' a concept propounded by McClelland asserts that the desire to achieve that is within the person decides the level of success, in the life. Students' academic life that has many challenging tasks demands that they are highly motivated in life to do well in studies. "Achievement motivation refers to the behaviour of an individual who strives to accomplish something, to do his best, to excel others in a performance" (Gupta, Devi, & Pasrija, 2012). "Achievement motivation is the attitude to achieverather than the achievements themselves" (Kumar & Bajpai, 2015). Higher is the level of achievement motivation, higher will be the academic success; lower is the level of achievement motivation, lower will be the academic success. The investigator, being a Teacher Trainee who had selected Geography, a major component of Social Science subject, in his graduation and post-graduation studies, has special interest and affinity, to pursue research in this

subject. In this research, he has attempted to make a comparative study of achievement motivation of X Standard government and private school students in Social Science curriculum.

Statement of the Problem:

“A Comparative Study of Achievement Motivation of X Standard Government and Private School Students in Social Science Curriculum”.

Operational Definitions of the Key Terms:

- ✓ Comparative Study: In the study, it refers to the comparison of academic achievement of X Standard government and private school students.
- ✓ Academic Achievement: In the present study, it refers to the extent to which the students of X standard government and private school students have motivations to achieve. It is measured by the score obtained the X Standard students in the Achievement Motivation Scale administered by the investigator.
- ✓ Social Science Curriculum: It refers to the content of the Social Science Textbook prepared by the Government of Tamil Nadu for the X Standard students.
- ✓ Government Schools: It refers to the government schools and government aided schools.
- ✓ Private Schools: It refers to the schools run by private organizations without getting grant-in-aid from the government.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the level of achievement motivation of X Standard government and private school students.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their achievement motivation in Social Science.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their achievement motivation in Social Science with regard to boys.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their achievement motivation in Social Science with regard to girls.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between government and private school X Standard Tamil medium students in their achievement motivation.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between government and private school X Standard English medium students in their achievement motivation.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to (a) Boys’ school and (b) Girls’ school and (c) Co-education schools.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their achievement motivation in Social Science.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their achievement motivation in Social Science with regard to boys.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their achievement motivation in Social Science with regard to girls.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard Tamil medium students in their achievement motivation.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard English medium students in their achievement motivation.
- ✓ There is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to (a) Boys’ school and (b) Girls’ school and (c) Co-education schools.

Methodology:

Survey Method was adapted for the study. In the study, all the X Standard students studying in Thanjavur, Pattukkottai and Kumbakonam Educational Districts form the population. The randomly selected 425 government school students and government-aided Schools students, and 425 private school students of X Standard, and altogether 850 students, form the sample in the study.

Tool Description and Data Collection:

The tool developed and standardized by the investigator and the guide (2015) ‘Achievement Motivation Scale’ was used in the study. A preliminary draft tool, with 50 multiple choice question items with four options, was prepared. After revision and establishing the content validity, ‘Pilot Study’ was conducted on 150 sample (75 government school students & 75 private school students) selected randomly from the 4 schools of Thanjavur, Kumbakonam and Pattukkottai Education Districts. Based on statistically calculated ‘Difficulty Index Value’ and ‘Discriminative Power Value’ of ‘Item Analysis’ process, 17 items were deleted and 33 items were selected for the final study. The score value 5 was given for strongly agree, 4 for agree, 3 for undecided, 2

for disagree and 1 for strongly disagree. The investigator directly administered the test and collected data from 850 sample and data were statistically analysed.

Statistical Treatment:

The collected data using 'Achievement Test in Social Science' were subjected to the following statistical treatment:

- ✓ Mean
- ✓ Standard Deviation
- ✓ t-test

Objective Testing:

Objective 1:

To find out the level of achievement motivation of X Standard government and private school students.

Table 1: Level of Achievement Motivation of X Standard Government and Private School Students in Social Science

Variable	Category	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Achievement Motivation	Government School	105	24.7	218	51.3	102	24.0
	Private School	96	22.6	226	53.2	103	24.2

It is inferred from the above table that 24.7% of government school X Standard students have low, 51.3% of them have moderate and 24.0% of them have high level of achievement motivation.

Regarding the private school X Standard students, 22.6% of them have low, 53.2% of them have moderate and 24.2% of them have high level of achievement motivation.

Hypotheses Testing:

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their achievement motivation in Social Science.

Table 2: Difference between X Standard Government and Private School Students in their Achievement Motivation in Social Science

Category	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks
Government School	425	101.08	26.412		
Private School	425	100.77	27.299		

(The table value of 't' is 1.96, NS - Not Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value (0.16) is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard students in their achievement motivation.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard boys in their achievement motivation.

Table 3: Difference between Government and Private school X Standard boys in their Achievement Motivation

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks
Government School Boys	200	102.85	26.460		
Private School Boys	225	102.35	26.971		

(The table value of 't' is 1.96, NS - Not Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value (0.19) is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard boys in their achievement motivation.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard girls in their achievement motivation.

Table 4: Difference between Government and Private School X Standard Girls in their Achievement Motivation

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks
Government School Girls	225	99.51	26.329		
Private School Girls	200	98.99	27.621		

(The table value of 't' is 1.96, NS - Not Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value (0.20) is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between difference between government and private school X Standard girls in their achievement motivation.

Hypothesis 4:

There is no significant difference between government and private school Standard Tamil medium students in their achievement motivation.

Table 5: Difference between Government and Private School X Standard Tamil Medium Students in their Achievement Motivation

Medium of Instruction	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks
Government School Tamil Medium	270	101.90	26.559	0.29	NS
Private School Tamil Medium	245	101.13	27.225		

(The table value of 't' is 1.96, NS - Not Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value (0.29) is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard Tamil medium students in their achievement motivation.

Hypothesis 5:

There is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard English medium students in their achievement motivation.

Table 6: Difference between Government and Private School X Standard English Medium Students in their Achievement Motivation

Medium of Instruction	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks
Government School English Medium	155	100.20	26.291	0.08	NS
Private School English Medium	180	100.43	27.425		

(The table value of 't' is 1.96, NS - Not Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value (0.08) is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard English medium students in their achievement motivation.

Hypothesis 6:

There is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to (a) Boys' school and (b) Girls' school and (c) Co-education schools.

Table 7: Difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to (a) Boys' school and (b) Girls' school and (c) Co-education schools.

Nature of the School	School	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks
Boys' Schools	Government	100	102	27.323	0.80	NS
	Private	110	98.91	28.271		
Girls' Schools	Go Government	115	101.36	25.862	1.17	NS
	Pri Private	110	105.39	25.814		
Coeducation Schools	Government	210	100.49	26.382	0.45	NS
	Private	205	99.29	27.390		

(The table value of 't' is 1.96, NS - Not Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value (0.80,1.17, 0.45) is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students studying in (a) boys' schools, (b) Girls' school and (c) Co-education schools in their achievement motivation.

Findings and Conclusions of the Study:

- ✓ The level of achievement motivation of X Standard government and private school students were found to be moderate
- ✓ There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their achievement motivation in Social Science.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard boys in their achievement motivation.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard girls in their achievement motivation.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard Tamil medium students in their achievement motivation.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private school X Standard English medium students in their achievement motivation.

- ✓ There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to (a) Boys' school and (b) Girls' school but not with (c) Co-education schools.

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